

*Downey et al. "Hay provision affects 24-h performance of normal and abnormal oral behaviors in individually housed dairy calves"*



Supplemental Figure 1. Perforated rubber mats placed on top of sand bedding from d 0-5 for all calves to reduce accidental sand inhalation